

An Example of Artistic Tendency in Examining the Relationship between Human Psychology and Physiology in Terms of Energy Balances

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evidence supporting the role of art in promoting one's health and well-being (Fancourt and Finn, 2019). In addition, the World Health Organization officially inaugurated its arts and health initiative, which will include organizing events, supporting research and raising awareness (Arts and Health). It is no accident, therefore, that this Research Topic, which added data on the psychological and physiological advantages of art, includes a commentary by Christopher Bailey, leader of the arts and health at WHO. Differences in the duration, frequency and intensity of physical activities can create significant differences in total energy expenditure. It has been shown that increases in activity-induced energy expenditure result in increases in total energy expenditure that are generally greater than increases in activity-induced energy expenditure. No evidence of spontaneous increase in physical activity measured by diary, interview, or accelerometer was found. However, this does not exclude increased physical activity that cannot be measured by these methods. (“Physical activity and energy balance - PubMed”) Part of the difference may also be explained by the increased metabolic rate after exercise. If changes in physical activity level affect energy balance, this should result in changes in body mass or body composition. It is found in body mass and fat mass in response to increases in physical activity induced by exercise training, which are usually smaller than predicted from the increase in energy expenditure. (“Physical activity and energy balance | Public Health Nutrition ...”) This shows that the training-induced increase in total energy expenditure is at least partially compensated by an increase in energy intake. There is some evidence that the association between energy expenditure and energy intake is less at lower levels of physical activity. (“Physical activity and energy balance - Cambridge”)

Keywords: *Human Physiology, Psychology, Relationship between Psychology and Physiology, Artistic Trend*

1. Introduction

Human physiology is in line with the first law of thermodynamics, which says that energy can be converted from one form to another but cannot be created or destroyed. (“How does hess's law follow the first law of thermodynamics?”) This law is usually formulated as:

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“rate of change in body ES 10”

It is equal to the difference between the EI and EO rates. All these terms are expressed as energy per unit time. EI consists primarily of chemical energy from the food and liquids we consume. EO includes radiant, conductive and convective heat lost; any work done; and latent heat of evaporation. ES is the rate of change in the body's macronutrient stores. (“Health and Nutrition Solution”) The energy balance equation ($ES = EI - EO$) is an expression of the energy conservation principle. "Increasing the level of physical activity for weight loss may therefore be most effective in the most sedentary individuals." (“Physical activity and energy balance | Public Health Nutrition ...”) A fundamental principle of nutrition and metabolism is that body weight change is related to an imbalance between the energy content of the food eaten and the energy the body spends to sustain life and perform physical work. Such an energy balance framework is a potentially powerful tool for investigating the regulation of body weight. (“Energy balance and its components: implications for body weight ...”) However, we need to better understand the components of energy balance and their interactions at various time scales to explain the natural history of conditions such as obesity and to predict the size and potential success of therapeutic interventions.

2. Data Collection on Prevention and Treatment in Clinical and Community Based Settings

This demand for evidence also includes studies of the social impact of the arts on families, neighborhoods and communities. (“Editorial: The Psychological and Physiological Benefits of the Arts”) These studies include research on implicit bias as well as the role that art plays in reducing social stigma. The final product is a collection of data on both prevention and treatment of the condition for both people and groups, in clinical and community-based settings, and throughout the lifespan. This research topic has attracted publications from all over the world on various aspects of the arts such as visual arts, music, dance and theatre, as well as studies on creative arts therapies such as music therapy , art therapy, drama therapy, dance movement. Therapy and

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integrated approaches thanks to an international editorial team specializing in art psychology and creative arts therapies . These publications cover a wide range of topics such as music therapy , art therapy, drama therapy, dance movement therapy, and integrated approaches. We also have research combining other forms of artistic practice, and our overview of these studies highlights the advantages of these joint treatments. This collection of research shows that the value of art lies in its ability to address and communicate health issues, as well as improve quality of life. Consequently, the need for national frameworks, such as those developed in the UK (Arts for Health and Wellbeing) and Australia (National Arts and Health Framework), to enhance the profile of the arts and health and promote better integration of the arts, is more practice across settings and agencies. has also been strengthened. When physical activity is performed, energy expenditure exceeds resting energy expenditure. *Activity-related energy expenditure varies with the muscle mass involved and the intensity at which the activity is performed. (“Physical activity and energy balance - PubMed”)*

3. Whole Body Energy Expenditure or EO Ratio

Absorbed carbohydrates, proteins and fats are converted in vivo into substrates that can be oxidized or stored to produce metabolically useful energy that drives biological processes. (“Energy balance and its components: implications for body weight ...”) The rate of whole-body energy expenditure, or EO, changes over a 24-hour period and throughout life. The energy spent reflects the fuels metabolized for growth, body maintenance needs, physical activity, pregnancy and lactation, and many other processes.

Drawing on a wide variety of research approaches, this collection not only reaffirms the importance of dedicating resources to conducting added research in the area, but also supplies important guidelines for deciding how to measure the impact of the arts on a society. Almost a third of the articles on this topic (23 out of 82) focused on either the visual arts, art therapy or phototherapy, which may be indicative of the proportion of art therapists in creative art therapies. Visual arts have also been the most studied art discipline. Even if we can only speak to the

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submitted articles, the abundance of articles focusing on the visual arts implies that the visual arts have a key role in improving health, avoiding mental and physical illness, and relieving both acute and chronic ailments . These populations included both healthy children and adults, as well as individuals suffering from psychiatric, neurological, and physical illnesses. This shows that artistic work can be done at any time and in any place. The studies included both short-term and long-term treatments. It should be noted that roughly half of these studies were carried out with the participation of children, families or art therapists working with children.

4. Systematic and Comprehensive Evaluations as well as Experimental and Relational Studies

Given the pervasive nature of the visual arts in infancy, it is not surprising that the emphasis is on young individuals. From an early age, young people are likely to be encouraged to paint, paint, sculpt and create, and it is a familiar and comfortable environment that children use when trying to express themselves. Studies have used a wide variety of research approaches, including empirical and correlational studies as well as systematic and comprehensive assessments . Examining the drawings made by children and adults both in terms of lecture and drawing technique is a method used in much research. There were also many studies that focused on the experiences of the participants. In articles written about the positive effects of taking part in the visual arts, a significant emphasis was placed on enhancing one's social and emotional well-being. For example, Alzheimer's patients who took part in a visual arts intervention were found to have fewer neuropsychiatric symptoms and a higher quality of life because of the intervention (Savazzi et al.).

Drawing has been found to help children regulate their emotions (Drake) and improve well-being in sailors in two separate studies. One study found that drawing faces in a museum-based program improves socio -emotional skills (Kastner et al.) and another study found that drawing promotes well-being in seafarers (Pipere et al.). Therefore, it is important to emphasize the potential emotional, cognitive and economic gains that can arise as a result of introducing the arts to schools

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and universities and workplaces as an overall improvement strategy. welfare . It can also refer to the potential benefits of the social prescription of the arts, investing in a creative economy, and using the arts as preventative measures.

The energy stored per unit body weight of carbohydrate, fat and protein varies considerably, especially when the associated intracellular water is taken into account. (“Energy balance and its components: implications for body weight ...”) In addition, dietary carbohydrate intake influences renal sodium excretion, which causes changes in extracellular fluid. Therefore, changes in body weight are expected when the macronutrient composition of the diet is changed, even if the energy content of the diet is kept constant. (“Energy balance and its components: implications for body weight ...”)

Long-term stability of body weight is generally considered an indicator of zero ES and thus energy balance. However, as described above, changes in body weight also include changes in body water, which may be variable, and thus weight change may not directly be energy imbalances, particularly in the short term. (“Energy balance and its components: implications for body weight ...”)

5. What are the Interactions Between the Components of the Energy Balance and How Are They Regulated? (“Energy balance and its components: implications for body weight ...”)

The 3 main terms of the energy balance equation change constantly over time. Beginning at conception , ES stays positive on average throughout growth and development. This positive energy imbalance is reflected by increased body weight. If adult weight is then kept over the long term, the average ES approaches zero and there is an approximate average state of energy balance. However, most adults gain fat throughout their lives and lose skeletal muscle later in life; The energy content of body fat replacement is much higher than that of lean tissue replacement. (“Energy balance and its components: implications for body weight ...”) Therefore, even with weight stability, most older adults do not have a "perfect" energy balance over the long term. During a 24-hour period, a typical person eats several meals throughout the day and their energy

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balance is strongly positive during and at once after each meal. Energy output is continuous but increases during sleep due to episodic physical activity and decreases. Energy balance is therefore highly variable over a 1-day period, and this variability is proved in dynamic changes in ES . Most adults also change their daily eating and activity patterns; therefore, the ES changes from day to day with the energy balance obtained only when averaged over longer time periods . (“Energy balance and its components: implications for body weight ...”)

The obligatory development of obesity requires an imbalance of positive energy above that needed for normal growth and development. A state of energy balance with similar short-term fluctuations in long-term intake and expenditure is approximated in obese individuals as in lean individuals, but in obese individuals this is achieved with a higher amount of body fat . Articles on art therapy and phototherapy focus on the positive effects of taking part in the arts on a person's mental health and relationships with others. Young people in the school setting were given the opportunity to openly express their feelings through art therapy (Harpazi et al.).

6. An Example of Physiology and Psychology Connection

individuals suffering from personality disorders take part in art therapy , it increases their emotional and social functioning (Haeyen et al.) and reduces anxiety and sadness in adults. This was achieved using art-based dynamic interpersonal therapy (Havsteen -Franklin et al.). In other research, the emphasis has been on the ways in which the creation of various art therapy approaches has the potential to improve mental health and overall health. For example, the collaborative sketching approach has been proved to aid adults in gaining a deeper understanding of intimacy and how they personally conceptualize intimacy (Snir et al.). It has been discovered that drawings of hearing households with deaf or hard of hearing children help to better understand family dynamics (Avrahami-Winaver et al.). The validity of art therapy methods was the subject of several further studies, all of which would nonetheless contribute to the field of art therapy practice. Kastner et al. created a tool for finding, recognizing and expressing emotions associated with traumatic situations. They later approved this tool. Wolk et al. interviewed young people to

CURRENT SCIENCE

learn about their experiences and thoughts on an art therapy practice designed to increase well-being . Art therapists respond to children and adolescents in a variety of ways , including eclectic, directive, and nondirective methods, according to the findings of a study conducted by Bosgraaf et al. and published as a systematic review. Eventually, Finkel and Bat- Or explored the basic concepts of running an open studio, but they discovered that practice could take many different forms. This was discovered during a scope review. Interestingly, the use of digital technologies is on the rise (Zubala et al.) and the inclusion of virtual reality has been found to clarify the needs of children and adolescents to cope with anxiety and depression (Shamri). Zeevi) and found to be favorably received by healthy adults. Both findings have implications for the treatment of mental health conditions in children and adolescents (Kamal et al.). Finally, the articles in this special edition come from a variety of nationalities and discuss the various elements of taking part in the visual arts from a multicultural perspective . A qualitative study of the feelings of art therapists working with hypertraditional children revealed significant perceptual and value-based differences between therapists and clients. These inequalities pose challenges and challenges for all involved and require therapists to have an elevated level of sensitivity (Keidar et al.).

Incorporating Chinese art elements into art therapy has been shown to help Chinese individuals with schizophrenia improve both their sense of self-efficacy and their ability to function socially (Tong et al.). The breadth and variety of influences attributable to dance and dance movement therapy, as well as those attributed to visual arts and art therapy, are documented as extensive in this research collection.

Older people took part in eight of the eleven studies on dance. For example, Hansen et al. investigated the effects of a dance intervention on older adults. On the other hand, Douse et al. and Shuper-Engelhard has conducted multi-generational interventions that prove the power of dance to unite not only families but communities as well. This appeal makes it clear that the benefits of dance and dance movement therapy for clinical groups should not be overlooked. There are five studies on dance movement therapy for adults with mental health problems (Hyvonen et al; Pylvanainen et al; Majore-Dusele et al; Payne and Brook; Kleinlooh et al); There is a study investigating the effect of dance movement therapy with children with Autism Spectrum Disorder;

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There are three papers investigating the effect of dance practices for Parkinson's disease (Fontanesi and DeSouza ; (Aithal et al.).

The counterpart to excess weight gain is a negative energy balance that leads to weight loss over time. For example, if an acute reduction in EI is kept over time, if behavioral patterns stay unchanged, changes in 3 processes—reduction of REE, AEE, and TEF—will also progressively lower EO as weight is lost . Eventually, these passive compensatory effects will lead to a diminishing energy imbalance with eventual restoration of a steady state at a lower body weight. (“Energy balance and its components: implications for body weight ...”)

7. Effect of Physical Activity on EI

If a person's energy needs can be met by the food they consume, it is generally thought that there must be a process that establishes a relationship between the amount of energy expended and the amount of food consumed. However , short-term trials in which participants increased their EO through physical activity did not reveal a compensatory change in EI for 1 or 2 days .

Low energy expenditure, sometimes known as a slow metabolism, is the root cause of obesity. In early research, resting energy expenditure (REE) was incorrectly adjusted by dividing body weight, resulting in incorrect reporting of the presence of a low metabolic rate in obese individuals. Because obese individuals have a higher relative amount of body fat with a lower metabolic rate than lean tissue, a simple division of REE by total weight leads to a lower estimate of mass-specific metabolic rate. Lean tissue has a higher metabolic rate than adipose tissue. As a result of this normalization error, the hypothesis was developed that a slow metabolism managed fat. The error is made much worse by the misapplication of the idea of energy balance, which can only be used correctly when applied at the whole-body level. Consequently, it is pointless to consider metabolism in terms of body weight per kilogram or even lean mass per kilogram since none of these measures are relevant to this system. It is not total food intake per capita that needs to be balanced against expenditure per kilogram; rather, it is per capita energy intake that must be

CURRENT SCIENCE

balanced against per capita energy expenditure. A lower REE per kilogram of body weight therefore cannot be a 'cause' of obesity.

Overall, motor outcomes were quite varied, from improved gait and balance (Fontanesi and DeSouza) to reduced body fat and elevated levels of physical fitness (Karkou et al.). showed, for example, that a dance intervention administered to breast cancer survivors in five different European countries had a positive effect on weight loss, right and left forearm circumference and hip changes, reduced 6-minute walking time, and supplied stronger right and left-hand grips. This work, along with others in this category, is a particularly effective strategy for improving motor control, as dance involves the whole body, can cheerfully promote physical improvements, and increase overall fitness. It is important to note that the motor improvements often achieved through dance and dance movement therapy are often accompanied by improvements in quality of life. This is exemplified by the fact that various dance-related motor changes can make it difficult to select a limited number of measures (e.g. , Karkou et al.). Another conclusion that applies throughout all our research on this topic relates to the social aspects of dance and dance movement therapy.

For example, Shuper-Engelhard used reflective diaries, video transcriptions, and interview analysis to assess the collaborative dance experience between grandchildren and their grandparents. According to the findings of the study, there was a more positive and more uplifting development in the mood of the grandmothers who danced with their grandchildren. According to research led by Sundstrom and Jola , playfully interacting with young grandchildren in the form of impromptu dances was found to be an important part of the lives of people with Parkinson's disease. This finding was thought to be quite interesting. Through qualitative one-on-one interviews with each participant, the authors explored the perspectives of people living with Parkinson's disease and their supportive care partners in the context of dance and beyond. This new method allowed participants to have an open discussion about their impression of dancing for Parkinson's programs, and many participants raised questions about the effect of dance on motor control. Despite this, several participants discussed how they could incorporate dance moves into their daily lives.

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Dancing also presented itself as a chance to interact with other people by sharing knowledge and comparing physical abilities; this is especially pertinent given the myriad unknowns about the disease. When used effectively, dance can have an impact on physiological states and expand psychological experiences. Dance can certainly help us focus our attention on our bodies, and when done properly, it can do both. For example, a psychophysiological study conducted by Tang Poy and Woolhouse discovered that seeing other people dancing simultaneously affects one's ability to appreciate beauty and causes pupil dilation, a measurement often used to decide how well a person is doing. Fontanesi and DeSouza used a psychophysiological measure, electrodermal activity (EDA), to measure emotional arousal in their experiments. The authors discovered that EDA was much greater when dancing as opposed to attending a fitness class. People with Parkinson's disease also reported significantly better levels of self-efficacy after dancing (including a beauty subscale) after exercise. This was the case even though both conditions were treated similarly. The authors conclude that the key aesthetic components of dance have the potential to alter emotional responses, as proved by both self-report and direct measurements from the body. The results of a multicenter, randomized controlled trial in Finland (Hyvonen et al; Pylvanainen et al) with over one hundred people suffering from depression supply convincing evidence of an increase in participants' psychological well-being. The results of this study give us reason to believe that the therapeutic benefits of dance may be important for both reducing depression scores and improving body image when people battling depression are treated by trained dance movement therapists .

These encouraging results are likely to be sustained for a period of at least three months after the completion of the intervention. Results from more limited pilot randomized controlled trials in Latvia and the United Kingdom point to beneficial effects. For example, a study conducted in Latvia (Majore-Dusele et al.) showed that women experiencing chronic pain and taking part in dance movement therapy groups experienced a reduction not only in the severity of their pain but also in their depression levels. experienced compared to the group treated as usual .

8. Physiological Expansion of the Sample

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The primary contributors to the typical one- to two-pound daily fluctuations in weight are changes in hydration and digestive tract content. Another limitation we met is that changes in body weight throughout a day and between days are not related to changes in energy stores. This is because changes in body weight are due to changes in hydration. Another limitation is that to calculate the energy deficit caused by a particular diet, it is necessary to have information about the amount of energy needed to keep body weight at the starting point. When the most precise technologies currently available are applied, the amount of uncertainty as said above is more than 100 kcal/d. Even if a person adheres to the diet exactly as prescribed, there will be substantial individual differences for weight lost due to unknown basic energy needs. For example, if the baseline energy requirement of an overweight or obese person is 100-200 kcal/d higher or lower than measured, perfect adherence to a diet will result in an error of 5–10 lb (2.3–4.5 kg). Projected weight changes over one year due to measurement error only. This error can occur even if the person adheres to the diet perfectly. Compared to other limitations, this poses less of a problem for research aimed at measuring mean differences between groups. According to the findings of a study conducted in the United Kingdom (Aithal et al.), children with autism received help from taking part in dance movement therapy groups, not only in terms of their social communication but also in terms of their overall health. This was true for children with both verbal and nonverbal skills . These designs include randomized controlled trials (Hyvonen et al; Majore-Dusele et al; Aithal et al); systematic reviews (as in the Dutch study on personality disorders); and econometric modeling (Kleinlooh et al.).

However, only a few studies relied solely on qualitative information (Sundstrom and Jola ; Kipling -Brown and Gray ; Payne and Brook); Interviews on user perspectives, autoethnographic approaches, and action research were some of the approaches adopted in qualitative research included in this article review . (“Frontiers | Editorial: The Psychological and Physiological Benefits of ...”) However, most of the studies included a mix of hard and soft data. Researchers seem to approach the subject of dance by paying attention to the subtle and internal as well as the quantitative and the external. This seems to be the most effective technique for studying a complex

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art form like dance. Overall, it seems that dance keeps us joyful, happy, and connected across generations and despite illness. The authors examine why it helps us psychologically as well as physiologically, and why dance is so beneficial for us. Studies on theatre, drama therapy, and psychodrama all include similar types of research, which you can read about here. Psychodrama, Drama Therapy, and Other Forms of Theater This Research Topic included ten studies that addressed how theater and drama-based procedures improve social and psychological health and specific issues at various points in a person's life. In one of two studies on theater, a quantitative study conducted in the United States by Panero and Winner suggested that acting students score higher on certain aspects of flow and empathy in their daily lives than non-acting students. This may suggest that acting leads to positive psychological experiences for those who take part in it. However, after the performance, the actors showed a significant increase in dissolution levels, which may be a sign of the harmful psychological effects of acting. In the opinion of the unbiased evaluators, not even one of these attributes had any effect on the overall quality of the performance. In Spain, Garca- Arch et al. conducted a quantitative controlled study showing that a 14-day performing arts program designed to change preconceived attitudes towards physical illness among the general population can be effective in reducing levels of implicit bias towards illness. The results of this study were published in the journal *Performing Arts in Medicine and Science*. A ten-week manual regimen for drama therapy was used in a mixed-method study to improve maternal insight and reduce the number of behavioral problems children show (Feniger-Schaal and Koren-Karie). According to the data, there is an association between an increase in maternal insight and a decrease in children's both externalized and general behavioral problems. A qualitative grounded theory method was used in another drama therapy study to explore the advantages of a 16-week group drama therapy protocol with youth classified as having an intellectual or developmental disorder (Musicka -Williams). The findings highlight the value of dramatic imitation not only as an entry point to dramatic work, but also in easing relational connections with others in the group. (“Editorial: The Psychological and Physiological Benefits of the Arts”)

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This value is emphasized by the fact that dramatic mimicry is both an entry point to dramatic work and eases relational connections. In a different mixed-methods study, the advantages of taking part in a drama therapy group for ten months were explored with ten individuals (Ray and Pendzik) associated with an autobiographical therapeutic performance, legal system . Results of pre- and post-interviews, as well as self-report measures, proved that participants experienced a sense of self-acceptance and understanding, empathy for others, and a potentially enhanced ability to take part in human service programs designed to increase work.

on interviews with experienced psychodramatists , Kushnir and Orkibi conducted a study on psychodrama in which they highlighted four benefits of embodying as a mechanism of change. These benefits include reducing the ambiguity of the problem, externalizing the protagonist's problem, strengthening the therapeutic bond between the protagonist and the therapist , and bypassing the protagonist's defense mechanisms.

The functionalization of the instantiation presented here may be valuable for future experimental research. In a different qualitative study from Israel, an open psychodrama group of battered women living in domestic violence shelters was found to reduce anxiety, tension, guilt, and self-blame while simultaneously supporting the participants' views of self-worth and confidence (Ron and Yanai). The purpose of the quantitative single-group pretest-posttest study conducted by Giacomucci and Marquit was to investigate the effectiveness of trauma-focused group psychodrama in the treatment of post- traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) in an addiction treatment facility in the United States . . Findings show a clinically significant reduction in overall PTSD symptoms ; however, this finding needs to be interpreted with caution, since there is no control group and clients are exposed to other therapies while being treated in psychodrama. Pires and colleagues studied the therapeutic use of masks made by five anxious teenagers as part of a psychodrama study using mixed techniques in Portugal. The research was done in Portugal.

Awareness, insight, self-understanding, empowerment, and relaxation were identified as the most important experiences participants had while attending the sessions. At the end of the research project, participants gave qualitative reports showing that they experienced a perceived improvement in calmness and world connectivity, enjoyment of interpersonal contact, and

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improved emotional expression and control. It is important to note that the mask approach is seen as fun and interesting. Testoni et al. conducted a study in Italy to investigate the impact of a death education initiative on 89 high school students dealing with acute grief as a result of the death of two of their friends. In addition to meditation, the intervention consisted of eight sessions, each having two hours of psychodrama, to help students elaborate on their feelings. According to a set of quantitative self-report measures, the intervention improved students' well-being, normalized death as something natural, reduced students' fear of death and associated avoidance, and reduced students' death avoidance. This research shows that theater-based procedures can increase our empathy, reduce prejudice, deepen awareness and self-acceptance, build relationships, and supply a sense of energy while also supplying a sense of relaxation. Some of the most important takeaways from this collection of research included the management of psychological distress as well as the development of abilities needed in social settings.

9. Metabolic Wards

There are more correct measurement methods that minimize the measurement error in inpatient examinations. For example, all room calorimeters can measure EO with 1-2% accuracy (22) and weighed, tracked food intake along with the measured stool produce very precise and precise EI readings. However, such research does not reflect free-living situations. Because humans typically cannot be kept in metabolic wards for such extended periods of time, it is difficult to conduct a comprehensive study of the dynamics of energy balance due to the characteristically long timescale (1-year part-time) in which changes in the human body occur. weight and composition. With the technology we currently have, we cannot watch EI or EO for long , even in the free-living environment. Therefore, all we can do is take "snapshots" of less than two weeks period.

It is important to note that the system used to keep energy balance is both interactive and complex. This means that a change in one part can affect one or more of the other components. The following key gaps that we are aware of were recognized by the panel as critical areas that need further investigation:

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“While we have a good understanding of the main aspects of energy balance through studies with shorter timeframes, we still have a lot to learn about how these aspects interact over longer timeframes. Therefore, we need longitudinal and longitudinal studies to learn the characteristics of the relationships between components of energy balance and changes in body composition and weight among children and adults.” (“Energy balance and its components: implications for body weight ...”)

10. Conclusion

Music Therapy and Music Narration The subject of fifteen studies within the scope of this Research Topic is the advantages of listening to music, producing music and receiving music therapy . There were five studies focused on music alone, ten studies focused on music therapy , and participants ranged from infants to the elderly. The research was conducted with participants with intellectual disability, dementia, depression, dealing with cancer and surviving the disease. The remaining experiments were performed using samples not from clinical settings. Research has been conducted using quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methodologies to explore the effects of listening to music and composing music . In addition, the effects of music on neurophysiological processes were examined in two separate studies. Improvements in well-being, quality of life, mood and emotion, anxiety, stress, and distress, as well as improvements in growth mindset were some of the results of listening to music and taking part in music therapy . It has been shown that both biological and psychological variables affect measurable aspects of energy balance. In most cases, however, they have been investigated separately; therefore, an integrated approach is needed. The relative influence of pre-digestive variables, also known as the cognitive and sensory effects of food and meals, on energy intake, energy balance, and physiological response to food is something to be decided. While our understanding of the broader effects of physical activity and exercise has been explored, we need to better understand the effects of various doses (volume, intensity, pattern, timing) and exercise types (endurance, resistance) on exercise.

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